

ReNEW

D4.6 - LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Synchro-modality City Logistics Hub

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning
4SHIP	4Shipping
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
APDL	Administração dos Portos do Douro
CC	Command Centre
CCNR	Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine
CEMT	Confederation of European Maritime Technology Societies
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DGRM	Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services
DT	Digital Twin
FMP	Floating Modular Platform
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HPC	High Performance Computing
IMEC	Interuniversitair Micro-Electronica Centrum
ING	Internationale Nederlanden Groep
ITA	Instituto Tecnológico De Aragon
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KNT	Konnecta
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
MAG	Magellan
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxides
OHB	Opleidingscentrum Voor Hout En Bouw Vzw
PAN	Panteia
RIS	River Information System
ROC	Remote Operation Centre
UGAL	Universitatea Dunarea De Jos Din Galati
VHF	Very High Frequency
WP	Work Package
ZES	Zero Emission Services

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1 Executive Summary

The ReNEW project brings together 24 partners from 11 different European Union nations, each one characterised by different background and expertise in their field, in order to achieve the ultimate goal of assisting transition to a smart, green, sustainable and climate-resilient inland waterway transportation. This document represents the first version of deliverable D4.1, due in M8, and aims to give an insight into the Overall Living Labs Implementation Plan and Management.

The ReNEW consortium includes four Living Labs. The first one is represented by Ghent's Multifunctional Synchronomodality Resilient City Logistics Hub and will operate in the Belgium inland waterways, starting from Ghent. The second, refers to the Douro Inland Waterway Infrastructure resilience and management in Portugal. The third Living Lab concerns the development of a resilience mitigation digital twin application and accounts for international waterways through several countries, such as the Netherlands, Belgium, France, Germany and Austria. The fourth Living Lab prescribes the operation of the innovative and under construction so-called X-barge, to be sailing in Belgium, France, the Netherlands, Germany and the Rhine region. All the aforementioned Living Labs will provide opportunities to test the innovative solutions and tools that will be developed essentially within the framework of WPs 2 and 3, in order to achieve the KPIs determined in WP1. In this direction, physical and digital tools will be deployed.

The purpose of this report is to give an overview of the Living Labs, more specific the Living Lab 1, and what objectives each one aims to attain. The existing physical and digital infrastructure is discussed, along with the available and on-demand data. Afterwards, there is an attempt to clarify the role of the involved partners and the way of their contribution, however keeping in mind the early stage of the project. Finally, an in-depth analysis of each use case is performed, to better explain the vision of the Living Labs and how the involved stakeholders are assumed to benefit from the novel technologies that will be developed.

2 Introduction

2.1. LL High Level Implementation Plan & Preparation

This document lays out a detailed and tailored Scoping and Implementation Plan that will be carried out in each of the 4 ReNEW LLs to help meet both the common project as well as the LL-specific objectives as per the Grant Agreement.

ReNEW is propelled by a core demonstration made up of four actual Living Labs that focus on various facets of Green Resilient Inland Water Transport (IWT). The goal of this core is to create the links required to build creative synergies and develop a thorough contextual approach to a strong and successful future for IWT.

ReNEW aims at overseeing the innovation development process from inspiration to commercialization within each Living Lab (LL). To achieve higher levels of innovative maturity, this will entail evaluating interim findings and adding feedback loops. During the proposal preparation stage, the initial ideation phase was already finished, and the results have been included into the descriptions of the LLs.

Each Living Lab (LL) has a specific implementation plan that was created using a multidisciplinary approach and information from a variety of disciplines, including engineering, economics, Technology, and inland waterway commerce. The goal is to use an interdisciplinary approach to analyse, synthesise, and create connections between many disciplines to provide cutting-edge knowledge and approaches connected to the project's findings. The end result will be the development of unique Green Resilient IWT Solutions (GRIWT), which will be used, tested, and improved in the four LLs shown in [Figure 1](#). In addition, the planning and design tasks involve a collaborative process within and between work packages, while also relying on information obtained from Living Lab (LL) stakeholders through the assistance of LL leaders and supporting partners. This iterative approach ensures that the planning and design tasks are continuously refined and improved based on input from various sources. In order to more comprehensively identify the needs and requirements of each LL, four distinct 3-hour technical workshops were arranged within the consortium, with substantial participation from various partners from the consortium. During these workshops, significant insights and valuable information were gained regarding the individual use cases of each LL. Simultaneously, the workshops facilitated the mapping of the identified needs with the technologies currently being developed within ReNEW, while ensuring that the project outcomes were always kept in mind. The initial mapping between the needs and the technologies within ReNEW was conducted using a tool developed by IMEC, one of the partners inside the consortium. The tool (Innovatrix) aided us in gaining insights as to what, why, who and how will each LL fulfil the objectives of ReNEW. ([Figure 2](#)) The knowledge and understanding acquired through these workshops

significantly contributed to the production of this document.

Figure 1 - ReNEW Multidisciplinary approach.

Figure 2 - The Innovatrix tool

2.2. Mapping the ReNEW Output

The purpose of this section is to map ReNEW's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverables as well as the Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1 - Adherence to ReNEW's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D4.6 LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Sychromodality City Logistics Hub v1		
Initial Design and Implementation plans.		
Task T4.3 LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Sychromodality City Logistics Hub		
The Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused by climate changes on the operations of the City Logistics Hub. (a) Implement Syncro-modality Solutions for Cities based on Infrastructure for Cargo Loading, to improve resilience and sustainability. The City Logistics Hubs will synchronize the arrival of the freight over barges with various transport modes that are compatible with the objectives of the City of Ghent to focus on quality of living and environmental sustainability. Solutions tested will include cargo bikes and electrical vehicles, that can move freight and people into and out of the city. Study the infrastructural setups and enhancements to support automated cargo loading. (b) Improve energy resilience with Power solutions innovations, including floating Batteries		
ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Chapter and Document (s) Description
T4.3 LL1 Ghent's Multifunctional Sychromodality City Logistics Hub	The Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused by climate changes on the operations of the City Logistics Hub. (a) Implement Syncro-modality Solutions for Cities based on Infrastructure for Cargo Loading, to improve resilience and sustainability. The City Logistics Hubs will synchronize the arrival of the freight over barges with various transport modes that are compatible with the objectives of the City of Ghent to focus on quality of living and environmental sustainability. Solutions tested will include cargo bikes and electrical vehicles, that can move freight and people into and out of the city. Study the infrastructural setups and enhancements to support automated cargo loading. (b) Improve energy resilience with Power solutions innovations, including floating Batteries	The objectives and scope of this task will be covered and presented as an initial overview on the 1 st version of this deliverable.

3 LL1 - Ghent’s Multifunctional Sychromodality City Logistics Hub

3.1 Context-Introduction-Key initiatives

The occurrence of extreme weather events has become increasingly common in the last number of years. A variety of extreme weather events, including droughts, rain induced landslides, river floods, winter storms, wildfire, and hurricanes, have threatened and damaged many different regions worldwide. This situation largely affects infrastructure systems and results in risk situations for people.

In Europe, events such as the last flooding in Germany in 2016, in France in 2016 - 2020, and in Belgium in 2021 are increasingly often creating threatening scenarios. Between 1998 and 2004 in Europe, floods caused some 700 fatalities, the displacement of about half a million people and at least EUR 25 billion in insured economic losses, (European-Commission (2004)). In addition, these situations occur not only more frequently but also reaching levels that were not previously foreseen. These kinds of perturbations often cause significant losses, which can last long period, from the moment when the perturbation starts until the total recovery.

In Figure I.1 , the increment in the number of occurrences of natural disasters is shown from 1984 until 2013. It is noted that this Figure also shows the direct damage (measured in USD billions) created by these perturbations.

Figure 3 - Graphical representation of the occurrence of several weather events, and total damage measured in USD billions. Source: The International Disaster Database, EM-DAT database. Martinez-Pastor,B, thesis.

The year 2020 is the warmest year in Belgium (measurements in Uccle - Brussels) since records began with an average temperature of 12.1°C, the Royal Meteorological Institute (IRM) announces.

An observation that goes with it: between 1833 (beginning of the observations) and today, the 10 warmest years in Brussels all took place after 2000.

“Climate change is also evident in the global average temperature for the past year 2020,” notes the IRM. “With a global average temperature increase of about 1.2°C (compared to the pre-industrial period 1850-1900), 2020 will be one of the three warmest years since global records began, according to the World Meteorological Organization. In addition, 2011-2020 is the hottest decade on record globally, with the six hottest years following 2014.”

Figure 4 - The 30 warmest years measured in Brussels since the meteorological measurement in 1833 – Institut Royale Météorologique (IRM)

In the summer of 2023, many heat records will be broken on the European continent, with disastrous consequences (forest fires, floods, drought, ...).

Figure 5 - ESA Earth Observation – Map showing Land surface temperatures reaching 46°C in Rome and Madrid and 47 °C in Sevilla. Source : <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/catalog>

To cope with all these exceptional circumstances, governments and managers of the infrastructures need to handle these circumstances and, unfortunately, in the field of transport, the number of tools dealing with these threatening situations is reduced.

Transport networks are a key element of a modern society, since human activity revolves around it. Among their main features are the capacity to move people and goods from one location to another, with the ability to move goods a very crucial factor.

Goods movements include the shipment of items such as (a) raw materials, including minerals, energy, food and other resources, (b) finished products, which need to be transported to the final clients and (c) also wastes, which is a vital role, with actions such as their removing and the prevention of their accumulation. This means that transport networks develop an essential function in our lives, making necessary their understanding and improvement.

An essential point about transport networks is their vulnerability. Since they are exposed to all sorts of perturbations, it is imperative to develop tools that explicitly consider the impacts of extreme weather events on such critical infrastructure.

In addition, these perturbations caused by natural hazards can be uncertain and vary during the lifetime. Despite this fact, there are models to predict natural hazards, but these predictions could not be accurate.

The resilience concept has been studied in different areas, i.e., ecology, socio-ecological systems, economics, urban infrastructure, telecommunication systems, water distribution systems, or internet protocol networks.

When resilience started to be analysed, the definition was mainly focused on the capacity of the system to absorb an impact. In this first approach, the concept of resilience did not include aspects which have been shown as crucial in its definition, such as the recovery process, and the time needed to reach again the normal operation of the network.

As more studies were developing in this area, the definition has become more complex, including in its definition aspects of the whole perturbation process.

In recent times, the holistic concept of resilience evaluates concepts such as the ability of a system to prepare and to adapt to changes, and the recovery pattern of the system.

Resilience – Literature review

The concept of resilience, according to Martinez-Pastor, B, is defined by the Cambridge dictionary as **“the ability to quickly return to a previous good condition”**. The origin of the word resilience comes from the Latin word “resiliere” whose meaning is “bounce back”. Resilience has been introduced in different fields of knowledge over the last 40 years, however, the use of this concept in the area of transport networks has been very recent

Holling (Holling, 1973) was the first author who studied the concept of resilience applied to the area of ecology, introduced the concept of resilience to the scientific world, defining it as “the ability of ecological system to absorb changes of environment variables”.

He describes the two different approaches as:

- **Engineering resilience** “concentrates on stability near an equilibrium steady state, where resistance to disturbance and speed of return to the equilibrium are used to measure the property”.
- **Ecological resilience** “emphasizes conditions far from any equilibrium steady state, where instabilities can flip a system into another regime of behaviour, that is, to another stability domain”.

The concept of ecological resilience is comparable to static resilience, which was later defined by Rose (Rose, 2007) as “a system’s capability to maintain its function”.

On the other hand, the engineering resilience can be compared with a dynamic resilience which refers to the rapidity with which a system returns to a state of normal function after a severe perturbation. This concept of dynamic resilience was understood by Pimm (Pimm, 1984) as “how fast the system returns towards equilibrium after a shock”.

In addition, some definitions from different areas are presented below:

- *Socio-ecological systems*. Carpenter et al. (2001) defined resilience as: “the amount of interruption that can be mitigated before the need to restructure the system or the ability of the system to deal with unexpected events without losing its characteristics”; and Walker et al. (2004) as: “the capacity of a system to absorb disturbance and reorganize while undergoing change so as to still retain essentially the same function, structure, identity, and feedbacks”.
- *Supply chains*. Christopher and Peck (2004) understood resilience as “the ability of a system to return to its original state or move to a new, more desirable state after being disturbed”.
- *Industrial safety*. Hollnagel et al. (2007) defined resilience as “the property of the system which gives the ability to recoup with system complication and sustaining its functionality under expected or unexpected event”.
- *Urban infrastructure*. Attoh-Okine et al. (2009) adopted the definition proposed in Branscomb (2006), understanding resilience as “the ability of the system to recover and adapt to

external shocks, which include natural intentional and technogenic disasters and failure due to poor design".

- *Telecommunication systems*. Omer et al. (2009) defined resilience as "the ability of the system to both absorb shock as well as to recover rapidly from a disruption so that it can return back to its original service delivery levels or close to it."
- *Water distribution systems*. Todini (2000) defined resilience as "the capability of the designed system to react and to overcome stress conditions".

Some differences can be identified when resilience is implemented in each of the fields presented, however, expressions found in the previous definitions such as "the capacity of a system to absorb disturbance", "the ability of a system to return to its original state", "the ability to recoup with system complication", and "the ability of the system to both absorb shock as well as to recover rapidly" will remain in the definition of resilience when applied to the Transport area.

Synchromodal Logistics – Literature review

Synchro-modality is an evolution of multimodal, intermodal and combined transport and it involves different and strongly integrated transportation modes. The aim is to provide a sustainable and, at the same time, efficient supply chain that reduces its environmental impact while optimizing resource utilization. Synchromodality builds on the vision of high-level flexible management of corridors proposed by intermodal transport to meet the wider interests of the whole supply chain, not only for a specific shipment or company. (Giusti et al., 2019)

To achieve synchro-modal transport the provision of real-time information is essential. In an environment of continuous monitoring and information availability of both the network and the cargoes, all stakeholders involved have the capacity to track their assets and make appropriate adjustments when necessary. The added value of information availability has been illustrated in the dynamic control and re-scheduling of railway traffic (Corman et al., 2017) or the re-assignment of tasks of fuel supply vessels inside and outside major hub ports (Christiansen et al., 2017).

Another essential enabler feature for synchromodal logistics is shipment flexibility that allows for some slack in managing and consolidating cargoes. Shipments are typically loaded on scheduled rail and sea services, while typically there is more robustness in road transport as road vehicles carry less capacity. In synchromodal bookings, transport is typically amodal, allowing LSPs to optimize the available capacities and provided there is information availability to effectively respond to any uncertainty and delays that might arise. To achieve that LSPs might consider the change of modes or prioritization of shipments. The value of flexibility is particularly important in the transport of perishable goods where when a delay arises, LSPs might assign a shipment to a faster mode, or choose to prioritize it over other less critical cargoes. The dynamic actions that LSPs can utilize to exploit the flexibility available in the system include rescheduling of shipments and if possible, transport legs, rerouting, prioritization and modal shift. Flexible synchromodal operations deliver can improved delivery reliability in case of disruptions while enabling dynamic adjustments also has significant cost and emissions savings benefits (Ambra et al., 2019).

To enable information sharing and flexibility in supply chains a certain level of stakeholder collaboration and coordination is required. From a stakeholder perspective, cooperation can be perceived as an integration of networks to improve consolidation of flows and increase overall delivery efficiency. Network integration can be vertical as in intermodal transport where vessels handle the intercontinental leg, while vans handle last mile delivery. However, in synchromodal logistics, horizontal network integration is also essential as it contributes to the routing flexibility (Tavasszy et al., 2017). Horizontal network integration directly impacts the availability of rerouting options, which in practice might convey to the use of a different vessel which alters the shipment's schedule, the use of a rail-leg instead of a sea-leg to expedite delivery, or bypass port congestion, or the use of a different intermediate multimodal terminal for short term storage.

Stakeholder collaboration is also a fundamental enabler for network information completeness and availability. Information sharing benefits all stakeholders involved, and especially LSPs who deal with planning of routing decisions and real-time adjustments, that are significantly impacted by improved quality and visibility of the supply chain. Cargo consolidation can be implemented as dynamic information about spare capacity become available (Schulte et al., 2017). Integration of data sharing has proven to be a tricky issue to address as several transport operators perceive data as valuable assets, and prefer to operate within organizational silos.

Synchromodality can also be a driver for the efficient operational management of assets extending beyond transport, to inventory management and production scheduling (Dong et al., 2018). Information sharing and synchronized decision making between various stakeholders can yield improved consolidation of cargoes, and improve utilization rate of assets. Ref: Kostas Zavitsas VLTN

Local situation in LL1

Ghent, the third largest city of Belgium, after Brussels and Antwerp, is located in the Flemish region of the country. One of the main cores of the city's economy is the Ghent port. However, a significant part of the freight's transportation is carried out through the city's canals and rivers (Figure 6). Consequently, the use of barges, accompanied with the relevant necessary infrastructure, plays perhaps the most crucial role in the transportation of goods and people.

Figure 6 - The Ghent LL corridors

In that direction, OHB, the local IWT community, has established two City Logistics Hubs, to test out novel synchromodal logistics arrangements. With the ultimate goal of minimizing and, in medium-term, eliminating the emissions from the vessels, the use of low/zero-emission and autonomous barges is definitely a necessary approach (Figure 7). New services and technologies will improve the operational efficiency by lowering the operational costs, enhancing competitiveness and expanding the navigational capabilities. Besides, innovative infrastructure will be deployed as solutions, based on autonomy developments with maturing green options. All these are combined to meet the project's utmost objectives: sustainability and resilience of inland waterways through the use of green-centric solutions.

Figure 7 - One of the OHB barges

The new infrastructures developed and tested within ReNEW will enable automated navigation and mooring of the vessels, as well as automated loading and unloading, all under the control of a Remote Operation Center. At this point, the key idea of exploiting a barge as a “floating battery” and off-grid power supplier needs to be highlighted, in order to provide infrastructures, vessels and hospitals with power in times of disaster, when the grid may go down. The infrastructures will be upgraded through the implementation of the following initiatives:

- Create and deliver a robust resilient mobile Smart Terminal, including the Modular Platform and Pontoons, to be used when necessary
- Establish a digital twin with shore back-up Remote Operation Center in Antwerp and Rotterdam, for smart navigation, and loading/unloading activities for the barges
- The Modular Platform, to be used as a means of transport and a power supply battery in emergency situations as well.
- Installation of sensors for environmental data gathering
- Automated sailing with 2 vessels
- Study of automated docking and automated mooring systems
- Remote operation for drones

All these are discussed further in the following sections of this chapter.

3.1.1 Vision and challenge to be addressed in ReNEW

T4.3: LL1 Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchronomodality City Logistics Hub

Lead: OHB; Partners: ISL, ITA, RDS, IMEC, AKKA, VLTN, ICCS, SF, UGAL, INLE (M3-M33)

Description of work: The Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused by climate changes on the operations of the City Logistics Hub. (a) Implement Syncro-modality Solutions for Cities based on Infrastructure for Cargo Loading, to improve resilience and sustainability. The City Logistics Hubs will synchronize the arrival of the freight over barges with various transport modes that are compatible with the objectives of the City of Ghent to focus on quality of living and environmental sustainability. Solutions tested will include cargo bikes and electrical vehicles, that can move freight and people into and out of the city. Study the infrastructural setups and enhancements to support automated cargo loading. (b) Improve energy resilience with Power solutions innovations, including floating Batteries. Test Ship and Shore digital twin solutions for autonomous mooring and Loading. *Perform the LL1 subtasks as described in Table 9.*

Challenges in the testbed Ghent

The city of Ghent has already adopted a vision note on the use of IW in his territory. In 2018, the City of Ghent and the water authority (De Vlaamse Waterweg) developed and approved a vision memorandum on 'water in the city of Ghent'. The vision memorandum 'Water in the city of Ghent' was approved on 04/10/2018 by the Board of Mayor and Aldermen, the City Council took note of the vision memorandum 'Water in the city of Ghent' on 17/12/2018.

This policy vision 'Water in the city' looks at the current and future role (and use) of water in Ghent from the perspective of 6 different challenges. We translate these 6 challenges for Ghent's water as follows:

- Provided with space for water against global warming, drought and flooding;
- Further expansion of the economy on and along the water;
- Stimulating sustainable mobility on and along the water;
- Strengthening Ghent as a city of water, to live/work/relax on and by water;
- Strengthening the green-blue backbone with water as an ecological axis in the city;
- Improving the water quality of Ghent's waterways.

This policy paper supports the will of policymakers to use the IW for economic purposes and thus contribute to the objectives of the Green Deal and sustainable logistics.

Ghent has a wide variety in IW : sea canal, canals, rivers, shallow water with controlled and tide waters. This an ideal testbed for different types of use cases.

The various types of IW are accessible to different types of ships with a different draft. The various watercourses have been mapped out for the various CEMT classes in an overview folder

Figure 4.24: payload capacity per waterway in City of Ghent

Figure 8 - Overview major canals in the city of Ghent

In the vision note different types of regulations and use of the IW are embedded.

Ghent has many inland waterways that are used by various users. To provide a good overview of all the functions and possibilities of this blue, public space, we developed 3 water maps. These are tailored to different types of users.

1. An updated tourist map provides information about water recreation
2. With the navigation map you know which vessel you are allowed to sail where, where you are and are not allowed to sail and an overview of the most important traffic signs on the water.
3. Mooring map with indication of the berths for houseboats and commercial shipping.

Sailing map

Berth map

Figure 9 - Sailing and berth map from the Visionnote of the city of Ghent.

We must take all these limitations and restrictions about the use of the water and infrastructure into account when elaborating the use cases for remote controlled sailing and mooring. Due to the large number of recreational users and pleasure craft on the water in Ghent's city centre, it is a particular challenge to set up remote co-controlled sailing.

Figure 10 - Map for tourists "how to use IW in Ghent"

Undoubtedly, a prerequisite to achieve the vision of ReNEW for highly resilient inland waterways demands innovations and going beyond the state of the art of the already existing green solutions.

To this end, integrating some of the emerging green technologies with advanced, original resilience-assist infrastructure, based on increased autonomy, is required.

Particularly, i) autonomous low or zero-emission barges, ii) use of floating platforms, for better manoeuvrable characteristics, platooning capability and emergency power supply capabilities, iii) several means of transportation of the cargo and people in case of disaster and iv) a shore module with an MCC, including a movable automation control centre, new automated mooring system and a floating pontoon with a modular land ramp are the main solutions to be delivered, to satisfy the scope of ReNEW, as regards the Ghent LL.

Nevertheless, it is expected that the outcomes and methodology adopted will be shared with other cities that are of interest for the LL1 inland waterways. Finally, the vision and the results of the Ghent LL contribute to achieving the impact targets set within the project while addressing the 5 common LL value indicators agreed for all the project's LLs.

Table 2 - Table overview Living Labs Common Value Indicators

Impact	LL1 Gent	LL2 Duero	LL3 Netherlands	LL4 GENT Duisport	LL4 Danube
Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	80%	80%	30-50%		
Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	90%	95%	80%		
20% increase in modal shift	20%	20%	10%	20%+	20%+
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	√	√	√	√	
Reduce environmental impact [CO2e]	90%	10%	10%	90%	10%

3.2 Existing infrastructure & Tools

3.2.1 Existing digital and hardware infrastructure

Given that one urban vessel of OHB already operates remotely by SEAFAR and the second is on the loop, the corresponding digital infrastructure already exists. Particularly, the autonomous ship sends the information to the MCC or to the shore centre of SEAFAR. LiDAR camera's and some sensors are already installed on the remote controlled ship, but more are definitely needed.

AIS monitoring system is available on the vessel. The AIS system delivers basic information about the vessel and the routing.

Figure 11 - Dashboard AIS data with vessel info

The AIS data from the test vessel AVATAR are framed in a dashboard (as developed by Rise – Axel Harteborn). With these data we can use measure the travel time, waiting and loading time at quays and use them in application scenarios.

AVATAR AIS Analysis dashboard

Figure 12 - AIS dashboard with analysis of the data from the AVATAR vessel

In addition, a 4G network is also disposable, allowing the exchange of indispensable data for the safe and remote navigability. On the 5G network there is currently still work to be done. In that sense, cameras and antennas are also available on the first vessel in a basic version. The connection with the ship's PLC goes over a gateway with 4G connection.

The research for using 5G private network is going on with the provider Proximus. A private network which provides the user total control over who uses this network

Different technologies are integrated into one connectivity experience: Critical Terminal, connectivity, tablet connectivity, smartphone connectivity, CPE backhaul, future integration with communication. This technology is secure, guaranteed and highly performant.

The 5G network is extremely suitable for controlling ships, drones, autonomously from a shore command center in a safe and ensured manner.

Figure 13 - Overview of the use of the 5G private network

It is easily understood that the digital tools which will be developed by the partners in WP3, will upgrade significantly the existing infrastructure and will aid to a more sustainable and efficient navigation of the barges.

3.2.2 Existing physical infrastructure

The existing physical infrastructure of LL1 is rather simple. OHB already owns 2 urban barges, while one is under construction. Moreover, there is an onshore command centre by SEAFAR to operate remotely the vessels. On the shoreside OHB collaborates with local logistic providers and has quays and infrastructure in the testbed Ghent.

Testing of the existing hardware for object recognition is essential for secure operations of remote controlled shipping. We also investigated the use of cameras to control the Smart Terminal and the various components, such as the mobile crane.

Several types of cameras are already tested in the first 6 months of the start of the project, in cooperation with several research institutions. These cameras are specific for object recognition on the water.

Figure 14 - LiDAR from TUDelft

Figure 15 - Test with cameras for UAntwerp

Figure 16 - Test sensor box and cameras for KUL

SEAFAR chooses another type of cameras to be used on the urban vessels:

Figure 17 - Seafar cameras installed on the urban test vessel

Remote control shipping

The level of automation can be defined according to several definition tables. For the use in Inland Waterways we refer to the next table.

	Level of automation ¹	Designation	Craft command (steering, propulsion, wheelhouse, etc.)	Monitoring of and responding to navigational environment	Fallback performance of dynamic navigation tasks
BOATMASTER PERFORMS PART OR ALL OF THE DYNAMIC NAVIGATION TASKS	0	NO AUTOMATION the full-time performance by the boatmaster of all aspects of the dynamic navigation tasks, even when supported by warning or intervention systems			
	1	STEERING ASSISTANCE the context-specific performance by a <u>steering automation system</u> using certain information about the navigational environment and with the expectation that the boatmaster performs all remaining aspects of the dynamic navigation tasks			
	2	PARTIAL AUTOMATION the context-specific performance by a navigation automation system of <u>both steering and propulsion</u> using certain information about the navigational environment and with the expectation that the boatmaster performs all remaining aspects of the dynamic navigation tasks			
SYSTEM PERFORMS THE ENTIRE DYNAMIC NAVIGATION TASKS (WHEN ENGAGED)	3	CONDITIONAL AUTOMATION the <u>sustained</u> context-specific performance by a navigation automation system of <u>all</u> dynamic navigation tasks, <u>including collision avoidance</u> , with the expectation that the boatmaster will be receptive to requests to intervene and to system failures and will respond appropriately			
	4	HIGH AUTOMATION the sustained context-specific performance and <u>fallback performance</u> by a navigation automation system of all dynamic navigation tasks, <u>without expecting a boatmaster responding to a request to intervene</u> ²			
	5	AUTONOMOUS = FULL AUTOMATION the sustained and <u>unconditional</u> performance and fallback performance by a navigation automation system of all dynamic navigation tasks, without expecting a boatmaster responding to a request to intervene			

Source: https://www.ccr-zkr.org/files/documents/AutomatisationNav/DefinitionAutomatisation_en.pdf

Figure 18 - Overview of the definitions and level of autonomy classification.

The concept of remote-control shipping

- Shore Control Center connect to one or more vessels using a single communication system
- Vessel provides Sensor data to Shore Control Center
- Shore Control Center sends control commands to the ship
- Communication System enables integration of authentication

Figure 19 - Model of remote control for a vessel.

In a remote-control setup, the communication layer between ship and shore is the most important component. It is used to secure the connection, to make sure that the commands arrive and to enable low latency communication. At the same time, connection failures show that the fallback routines for the remote control must also exist.

When a vessel is remotely controlled, a remote operator must always have a complete overview of the situation. This enables him to intervene immediately in a critical situation. At the same time, the remote operator must be familiar with the interface and the control system, so the functionality must be abstracted, and a single interface must be used for different vessels. Technical details such as thrusters, rudders or maneuvering thrusters must be combined and represented in a uniform way in order to standardize the overall behavior of different ships under the same remote-control commands.

We have already tested in LL1 Ghent the several possibilities to make remote control managing of vessels possible.

Figure 20 - Real life testing of the remote control from shore control center of the AVATAR vessel

Testing remote control steering a ship has many challenges. We have learned from the tests with other types of vessels where steering is done line-in-sight and the skipper in the shore control center can see the test vessel.

The next step is to equip the urban boat for remote control at a great distance from SF's shore control center in Antwerp.

The SF's shore control center in Antwerp is fully equipped with technical installation that can connect to the equipment on board a ship to receive data and control the ship remotely. In the bridge ashore there is an experienced captain from the commercial shipping industry who will steer the ship remotely.

Figure 21 - Shore Control Center of Seafar - Foto : De Standaard 16 april 2023

3.3 Data collection

For the completion of the work carried out for the use cases of Ghent LL, several kinds of data are needed. Environmental data are probably the most important, since they are directly linked with the resilience and sustainability concepts. Moreover, the data concerning the availability of the vessels (by OHB and SEAFAR) as well as the data for the cranes' location (onshore or on the vessel) and operation, the data for the floating battery and fuel consumption will be managed. In this way, the sensors, that will be deployed on the vessel, will absolutely have an essential role, since they are required for the remote operation of the vessel and their autonomous mooring. Additional sensors, camera and hanging equipment for the autonomous crane may also be necessary. All the data collected will be available for further investigation.

Finally, innovation in data management shall be remarked, since it will include smart navigation system with GPS as well as with the use of Copernicus/Galileo for positioning and navigation purposes. Overall, there will be data streaming from LL to the cloud and the (Mobile) Command Centre.

3.3.1 KPIs

The aimed KPIs in the framework of the Ghent LL, are accordingly described next. Primarily, with the completion of the project, a navigability capacity improvement of 80% is targeted. After all the digital and physical tools are designed, developed and installed, a great increase of 90% of the infrastructure resilience should be remarked, along with a 20% augmentation in modal shift. In addition, a smooth passenger mobility operation will be ensured. Finally, perhaps the most crucial KPI to be met is the drastic reduction of 90% of the IWT environmental footprint, in terms of CO_{2e} emissions. These KPIs are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 - Ghent LL Impacts and Target KPIs

Impacts	Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	20% increase in modal shift	Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	Reduce environmental impact [CO _{2e}]
LL1 Ghent	80%	90%	20%	✓	90%

- **Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50 % capacity during extreme weather events – 80%**
 - o Guaranteeing the navigability of inland waterways depends on external circumstances and stakeholders, in particular the water authority that ensures that the locks work, that the water level remains normal, that excess water can be discharged to the sea, etc.
 - o During extreme weather conditions, such as water bomb or heavy rainfall, certain parameters will not be able to be maintained. Due to the specific design of the ship and the remote control, we want to ensure at least 50% capacity of the navigability of the waterways
- **Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions – 90%**
 - o It is not easy to improve the resilience of land and sea infrastructure to extreme weather conditions and man-made events, because while these structures are robust, the human factor needed to drive them needs to be managed. and to check, is the weak link that can fail. Due to the far-reaching plan of automation of various parts of the infrastructure, we want to ensure at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions
- **20% increase of modal shift**
 - o The intention is to increase the tonnage transferred from road transport to waterborne transport through concrete collaborations with various stakeholders. In doing so, regional transport by using IW and the transport of goods in an urban environment will

be examined. This modal shift will in turn contribute to the reduction of CO₂ and NO_x emissions.

- **Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport**
 - o Maintaining the smooth operation of passenger mobility and freight transport in an urban environment depends on many factors. By building a resilient system where, in the event of a disaster, large parts of the operation can be taken over by an automated system, it will guarantee that the operation can be guaranteed.
 - o An analysis of existing IW mobility in Europe with small vessels for cargo transport will help to have insight in the problems of citydistribution using IW and last miles solutions.
- **Reduce environmental impact (CO₂ and Nox) – 90%**
 - o By using electric motors in the urban vessels, we can say that the emissions of CO₂, NO_x, and other pollutants that are released when using an internal combustion engine will reduce these emissions by 100%.

3.3.2. Stakeholders and their role

The main stakeholders and the activities to be performed for the Ghent LL, are described below.

OHB: OHB is the urban barges owner and will participate in the design of the FMP. Overall, OHB will coordinate the implementation, in close cooperation with SEAFAR and UGAL.

SEAFAR: SF, a well-known remote operator of automated and semi-autonomous vessels in Belgium, will provide the remote-control technologies, from onshore control centres, and expertise for increased resilience. They will support the LLs with commercial services and impact pathways. SEAFAR will install their equipment and remotely navigate the vessel from the headquarters in Antwerp. The captain will have in front of him 6-8 monitors (with information and systems but not mobile).

UGAL: The research team from UGAL will design and validate the pontoon and generally the whole structure of the FMP. UGAL will also support the construction and operational activities. A series of technical meetings have already been organized to discuss details about the design of the FMP.

IMEC & KNT: IMEC and KNT will work towards the development of the necessary digital infrastructures. Particularly, local digital twins, dataspace and generic digital twin architecture fall within their contribution to the project. Finally, they are supposed to provide knowledge regarding the operational side and deployment of the tools.

ICCS : ICCS has extensive experience with state-of-the-art in-situ sensors measuring the water level and quality. The implementation of synergistic framework allowing the combination of in-situ data with satellite altimetry data is important in estimating the deployment of rescue equipment and people in the affected area.

Akkodis : The team of Akkodis will help with the development of the dronesystem on the rescue vessel, that will help to map the environment of the disaster area and pass on data to the CC of any victims.

ITA: Work out Application Scenario’s (AS) - will set up KPIs for the LL use cases using DT, Data Spaces, and ReNEW services and Solutions Deployed, Simulation Libraries, Simulated models at the level of Proof of Concept.

Sintef Ocean : will provide advice on development of a remote controlled or automated mooring system, based on their experience on conducting feasibility studies on similar systems for ferries and short sea ships.

In any case, the role of each partner will be better understandable through the following sections.

3.4 Use cases

Methodology

We want to use the Design Thinking Method for developing the several usecases. Design Thinking is a method to generate solutions that focuses its effectiveness on understanding and solving the real needs of users.

According to Tim Brown, current CEO of IDEO, Design Thinking "is a discipline that uses the sensitivity and methods of designers to match the needs of people with what is technologically feasible and what a viable business strategy can turn in value for the customer, as well as a great opportunity for the market. " Companies like Apple, Google or Zara use it.

Being a great generator of innovation, it can be applied to any field. From the development of products or services to the improvement of processes or the definition of business models. Its applicability has as limits our own imagination.

Figure 22 - Design thinking methodology

The design thinking methodology follows five steps as shown in the figure.

The objective of these workshop is to help project team and designers to understand together and define in detail the product perspective and features, the user classes and characteristics, the operating environment, the design and implementation of constraints and the user documentation requirements. In addition, the usage scenario will be defined. This definition will compile the different user profiles, the use cases and special usage considerations.

3.4.1. Use case 1: Smart Terminal

A Smart Port is a port that uses automation and innovative technologies including Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data, Internet of Things (IoT) and Blockchain to improve its performance.

Although the industry of ports and container shipping is often regarded as conservative and resistant to change, there are new technologies, systems and solutions emerging that will alter this perception in the coming years, leading the entire sector to a brighter, more connected future.

The industry has already embraced many emerging technologies such as Digital Twins, cargo flow optimisation and visualisation – giving customers end-to-end transparency of their cargo’s journey through the supply – and the emergence of 5G’s low latency and faster connectivity to improve port operations. More info on www.porttechnology.org/news/what-is-a-smart-port/

The work carried out in the framework of Use Case 1, aims to design and build a “Smart Terminal”, for increased resilience. The objective of the Smart Terminal is to ensure the connection between an autonomous barge and the shore, on a remote-control way, along with the development of a (Mobile) Command Center, to be used under crisis circumstances.

The MCC can be considered as a digital backup with the SEAFAR onshore system in Antwerp. In crisis, it will be deployed and transferred outside of the affected area, within a short time. Consequently, the resilience part for use case 1 will be covered by the fact that the management of the terminal, as a whole, can change within a certain amount of time.

In more detail, the autonomous vessel will send the information needed to the command center or the onshore centre of SEAFAR, which in both cases will be stored on the cloud. Meanwhile, the skipper or the captain is assumed to perform the management of the vessel navigating it in the river or canal behind a desk in the office. The visualisation of the vessels’ routing will most probably be implemented through a dashboard. This process is effectively reflected in Figure 23.

Figure 23 - The skipper or the captain navigating remotely the vessel, from the onshore command centre

Usecase1 consists of different parts that are developed separately from each other, to be merged later into a resilient smart whole:

Smart Terminal.

The "Smart Terminal" is a set of "intelligent" parts that together form a smart whole. On the one hand, the terminal consists of the remote-controlled ships that are also controlled from the CC in terms of mooring and positioning, so that they can be unloaded. On the other hand, the urban vessel also has to implement a remote controlled loading and unloading system on board that is mobile and can be driven on and off the ship. From landside it can then be used in emergency situations, without a crane operator, to load or unload people and material. The final component of the Smart Terminal is the use of a remotely controlled drone that can carry out inspections in a hazardous area without the direct intervention of a physical person.

Smart ship

The most important part of the Smart Terminal is the ship that will be designed to carry out the removal of people and goods from the danger zone on the one hand, and the loading of rescue equipment and rescuers on the other. Together with the nautical architects and engineers of UGal, OHB will work out the best application to design a multifunctional ship that can be deployed in various circumstances.

Much attention will be paid to the construction of the SF equipment and the connectivity between the PLC on board the ship, which will capture the control commands and forward them to the CC on the shore side.

The automated vessel comprises three main elements: a vessel operated remotely by captains located elsewhere, a communication system that enables data exchange between the vessel and the remote operation center, and the remote-control center itself.

Multiple teams within Seafar will participate in this endeavor, including the hardware engineers responsible for installing new equipment related to the project's scope.

The software team will be in charge of integrating the new hardware into the Human-Machine Interface, while the network engineer will ensure data transmission.

Finally, the remote-control center, situated at Seafar's premises, will serve as the central hub where remote captains utilize AI-powered tools developed by Seafar's engineers and researchers.

Object detection might be considered for improved situational awareness of the remote captain.

Remote controlled mooring – Station keeping

In this scenario it is necessary to develop a remote controlled mooring system for the urban ships. The ships will be equipped with bow and stern thrusters, in addition to the normal propulsion line, so that they are able to remain in "station" mode waiting to dock with other vessels or at the quay.

Existing automated mooring systems have been investigated by SO for ferry and short-sea applications by Bellingmo & Jørgensen (2022) and Bellingmo et al. (2023). These solutions are not fit for purpose to smaller inland barges. However, the main parameters and constraints that are important for selection of automated mooring systems for small inland barges are in principle similar and can be used in the selection process of an automated mooring system for the urban barge in LL1.

Due to the knowledge of Sintef Ocean in the field of autonomous mooring, a study will be made with them about the different systems for mooring a ship from remote control. Most existing systems are made for seagoing vessels and not yet for smaller vessels operating inland.

Based on this study, it can be decided to use an efficiently applicable mooring system, which will also increase the resilience of the operations.

Remote controlled loading and unloading system

A multi-user and multifunctional loading and unloading system will be designed to load the vessels on a semi-automated way, in function of the rescue scenario's which will be designed. OHB has already laid the foundations for a study that should provide insight into which type of loading and unloading system can be used in situations where personnel can fail in a cascade role due to the impact of a disaster. The loading and unloading system is part of the whole "smart terminal" in which ship, mooring, land infrastructure, cargo and people are interrelated.

To increase the resilience of the loading and unloading system, a flexible mobile loading system that will operate from the ship instead of the landside can be used. The advantages here are that work is not done from 1 charging point in the city, but that the entire city in a disaster area can be reached and goods and people can be loaded and unloaded at the places where this is most efficient.

SF, Imec and OHB will examine how the control of the machines (crane, drone and loading platform) can be taken over from the remote-control operating system that comes with the machines to the cloud for the web-based application, so that the captain in the CC can control the and management can take over.

Imec will investigate the feasibility of establishing a connection between machines like the loading and unloading system and the mobile command centre. Our focus lies in researching and possibly developing a client application that serves as an interface to communicate between these two systems. It is important to clarify that Imec's role is limited to this research and development of the connecting client only, without involvement in the creation of machine-to-machine communication technology or remote-control operations. When this would not be possible (e.g. due to limits of the technology), we could incorporate certain data of the machines into the Digital Twin, such as its position and its operational status, when they would be available.

Drone as "eyes in the sky"

Using a drone in a disaster area makes sense. Due to the failure of personnel and perhaps also communication channels, the information from the disaster area can be limited. The more information can be collected and passed on to the captain in the CC who has to make the decisions, the more accurately the assistance can be deployed.

The data that a drone can collect can be very diverse, ranging from positioning of the ship, research into objects or bodies in the water, information about a fire or toxic cloud, infrared detection in search of survivors. It is also a challenge to have the drone coupled in an automated way with the ship's power supply and the Dataspace to pass on the information to the CC. The drone is controlled by the skipper, and if the skipper fails, the command is taken over by the captain of the CC.

Multifunctional transportbox

OHB will develop a universal transport box that is intended to be used by the remote controlled loading system. The normal loading systems (pallet, IBC box, Danish trail, big bag,...) are not suitable for remote pick-up. Due to the precision of the inclusion of such a loading device, the crane operator's presence next to the crane and the object to be loaded is necessary. We would like to develop a sustainable, flexible, resilient and multi-purpose tool that can be used in many autonomous logistics operations.

Mobile Command Center

All the data and the command management will be sent through and stored in a web-based interface, which can be managed on a tablet. In the test scenarios (for example to measure the impact of floods on the logistic infrastructure) the "command center" in the cloud can be transferred from the Seafar CC to any other place outside the disaster area to ensure continuity of the operations. In this scenario the management of several ships and all independent parts of the smart terminal can be transferred in a certain amount of time outside the danger zone.

In order to remotely operate the barge, data must be transferred from the vessel to the onshore control centre. The MCC is expected to receive and handle data from a variety of sources, such as from the ship, infrastructure, people and automation-related processes. In the latter case, a remote-control system for a crane fixed onshore or mobile on a vessel is anticipated to be attempted. All these are graphically represented in Figure 27.

Figure 24 - A general overview of how the MCC will work. Inputs and outputs

In this context a local digital twin will be developed. A local digital twin is a digital representation of a complex system that models the physical, social and economic factors and interactions between them that make up that system. They provide a comprehensive view of a geographical area's infrastructure, resources and behaviours and can be used to simulate various scenarios and make data-supported decisions to improve geographic planning and management. (source: Local Digital Twin | Living-in.eu | <https://living-in.eu/groups/solutions/local-digital-twin>)

As the data and models required to develop this local digital twin stems from various stakeholder within the ecosystem of the city logistics hub, the data publishers may want to retain in control of the data that is being exchanged. Hence, a data space technology may be an appropriate way to ingest the required data into the local digital twin. A dataspace is defined as a decentralized infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing and exchange in data ecosystems based on commonly agreed principles. A dataspace provides a foundation for developing data-driven business models and services, while also ensuring privacy, security, and sovereignty over data. (source: Deliverable 3.1)

The partners from Work package 1, 3 and Living Lab 1 are working on a backlog with user stories to translate the Implementation plan into tangible requirements for the Data Space and Digital Twin. The feasibility of the Digital Twin requirements will be assessed accordingly.

More specifically, all the different types of data, such as barge data, weather data, pandemic amongst others, will be stored in a local digital twin. These tools will be designed within WP3. Afterwards, different types of models will be developed and accordingly incorporated in the local digital twin. The local digital twin will act as a decision support tool, both in real time, estimating the short- and long-term impact of climate disaster on the City Logistics Hub, and a what-if scenarios tool, to assess the potential consequences of extreme and cascading effects. In any case, this decision support tool will be used to simulate and create scenarios. Figure 28 shows a high-level overview of the local digital twin and dataspace to be deployed, enriched with all the feasible interconnections.

Some parties that could be involved in crisis situations management and could exploit all the aforementioned tools are of course the city of Ghent and every relevant city, water authorities, emergency services, governmental institutions public services and crane and logistic operators.

Figure 25 - Dataspace components and the local digital twin. The graph depicts also the interlinks of the digital tools with the various data sources and models

The partners in Work Package 3 will develop the building blocks to establish a local digital twin for the Ghent Living Lab. This digital twin will serve as a visualization tool, capturing and displaying data generated by the various use cases within the Ghent Living Lab. Among the data sources that could be visualized are the FMP data, smart terminal data, information from sensors, and other relevant sources. By aggregating and storing this data in a dataspace, the information becomes accessible to interested parties beyond the immediate Living Lab’s scope.

The purpose of the digital twin lies in acting as a comprehensive dashboard, providing a holistic view of the Ghent Multidisciplinary Logistics hub's operations. The digital twin will bring together the diverse data streams, allowing users to gain valuable (near) real-time insights into the ongoing activities and processes, reaching an ambition level 3 (source deliverable 3.1). Furthermore, the digital twin has potential to enable users to create and simulate scenarios (ambition level 4), for example the impact of extreme weather events on the logistic hub, improving decision-making. The partners from Work Package 3 will (co-)develop the digital twin, and the necessary connectors to the data sources, but will not carry out the development of the simulation models. The aim is to ensure that these simulation models are made accessible and available through the local digital twin. A precondition is that the scenarios required to run these simulations are made available as well.

Imec aims to set the foundation for an innovative and data-driven approach to managing the Ghent Living Lab and its Multidisciplinary Logistics hub. Swift access to relevant data sources is crucial for the partners of Work Package 3 to initiate the development of the digital twin effectively. In instances where certain data sources are not yet available, it is essential that documentation is provided to imec (e.g. regarding the API). This documentation should allow the partners from Work Package 3 to carry out the necessary work on their end and integrate the data seamlessly once it becomes accessible.

3.4.2. Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform

A very interesting case that will be studied within the Ghent LL is the design of a Floating Modular Platform (FMP). This platform will contribute to the concept of resilience significantly, in a sense that it is expected to be used as an emergency means of transport as well as a power supply source owing to the battery that it will be equipped with, i.e., urban battery. The FMP is practically a floating platform-pontoon, that could be used in many ways as f.ex. a floating battery system or even a floating hospital.

The FMP, as a whole configuration, is considered as a floating pontoon, possibly interacting with the 2 or 3 barges of OHB, when needed. Apart from the battery, it will also include automated mooring systems and ramps, a resilient loading system as for ex. a crane to move containers with freights or remove obstacles. Nevertheless, the new automated mooring system remains a challenge, though an aim of the project, due to its high cost of design and installation. The FMP will work during riotous situations, such as floods and long dry periods, maybe even in case of diseases, thanks to the modular hospital that the pontoon can be used as. UGAL, OHB and SEAFAR will closely collaborate to implement a smart navigation system and contribute to the automation of ramp and mooring system. Last but not least, the FMP will assist to the development of autonomous platooning capability for the 3 barges of OHB. It will be designed with the vision to benefit as many entities as possible, since except for the residents of the cities nearby the rivers/canal, rescue public services, logistic providers and crane operators shall also be involved.

As far as the design and implementation of the FMP is concerned, an initial study has already been performed by UGAL. The FMP configuration is slightly different, compared to the one initially conceived. The final one is more flexible and consists of one pontoon and three urban barges, from which two already exist and one is under construction.

From the Naval Engineering point of view, the design and validation of the FMP requires laboured and time consuming processes, like hydrostatic and stability calculations, hydrodynamic numerical simulations (resistance, propulsion, manoeuvrability, ship motions) and strength analysis for several loading cases. The hydrodynamic numerical simulations prescribe mostly the use of CFD codes (for either potential or viscous simulations). These runs will be executed with the use of an HPC and

dedicated software, by UGAL. Some initial results of the CFD simulations are shown in Figures 26 and 27.

Figure 26 - CFD simulations for the FMP

Figure 27 - Different contours from the CFD simulations of the FMP

Given the lack of data for the hydrodynamic and structural behaviours of the urban barges, it is needed to start the calculations with the geometry of one urban barge and then investigate different configurations, for the total formation of one pontoon with ramp, crane and three barges. Even though wave resistance does not exist in rivers and canals, hydrodynamic and hydrostatic calculations must be performed, due to surface ripples of the river. The calculations will be performed for all configurations, of all speed ranges, also in shallow water, for different loading cases (local and global strength analysis). These results will be validated against experimental ones.

During the study and preparatory phase of the development of the Floating Pontoon or the rescue vessel, extensive testing can already be carried out with the existing urban and research vessels of OHB in order to gain experience and share knowledge that will contribute to a mature concept.

The UGal and SF engineers will check to what extent the pontoon, which does not have a propulsion system or an intra-electricity grid, can be displayed on the map. The captain in the onshore CC must be able to observe the pontoon on his instruments so that he can steer the urban vessels, equipped with remote control equipment, from and to the pontoon in a safe manner. Mooring on the pontoon of the urban vessels is also a challenge for which a solution must be found in collaboration with SF.

Short description of results regarding the hydrodynamic and structural analysis of urban barge

(i) The first step consist in hydrostatics and stability computation in order to ensure that the barge is designed to withstand various loads, external forces, and environment conditions while maintaining its safety and stability. In table 4 are given the loading cases considered at this chapter.

Table 4 - Overview loading scenarios

Table . Loading cases		
Loading Case	1. Light ship	
	2. Medium load	
	3. Full load	
Loading Scenarios	Passengers	4. 50 Passengers
		5. 60 Passengers
		6. Ballast tank & 70 Passengers
	Container	7. 1 Container
		8. 1 Container & ballast tank
	Truck	9. 1 Light truck
		10. 2 Light tracks
	Crane	11. Crane
		12. Light crane & ballast tank

Considering the request of OHB to analyse the possibility to transport 60-80 passengers, evaluation of the stability considering the ship heeling due to the crowding of passengers in one bord lead to the conclusion that urban barge is capable to carry up 50 passengers without supplementary ballast and 70 passengers with ballast. , various scenarios including a crane onboard were analysed and recommendations were made based on the weight of the loaded and unloaded cargo to ensure a safe working load.

(ii) The second step is represented by the Computational Fluid Dynamic study, that was performed to estimate the total resistance of the urban barge sailing in calm water at different speeds taking into considerations only two degrees of freedom, which are the vertical translation in z-direction, known as sinkage and the rotation around the y-axis, known as trim. A side from the resistance prediction, a special focus was on pressure distribution on the hull, free-surface prediction, flow configurations, flow wake, separation, and vortices formation, in the scope of understanding and enhancing the hydrodynamic performance of the urban barge. In Figure 28 are depicted the urban barges configurations used in hydrodynamic numerical simulation.

Figure 28 - Urban Barge configuration in the simulation cases.

The next table summarizes the various simulation cases performed in the hydrodynamic investigation. In total, the number of performed cases is within 156 cases.

Table 5 – Simulation cases for LL1

Table : A summary for the simulation cases performed.

Simulation Cases								
Urban Barge Speed [km/h]	Urban Barge in Deep water				Shallow Water Effect			
	UB	2 UB SBS	2 UB C	3 UB C	h/T = 1.2	h/T = 1.5	h/T = 2.0	h/T = 3.0
7	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
8	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
9	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
10	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
11	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
12	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
13	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
14	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗

✓ performed ✗ not performed

where:

h -water depth,

T - draught of the urban barge,

UB - urban barge,

SBS - side by side,

UB C - Urban Barges in convoy.

The local flow of the Urban Barge sailing at draft $T = 0.8$ m can be visualized in Figure 34 where the underwater configuration of the iso-surface second invariant $Q = 10$ is presented and coloured by the nondimensional helicity to observe the vortical formations and the flow characteristics of the barge.

Figure 29 - Second invariant $Q=10$ coloured by nondimensional helicity for the UB sailing at 13 km/h at $T = 0.4$ and 0.8 m

The power prediction for the Barge sailing in convoy or side by side was also tested and showed the increment of the effective power. For 2 Urban barges, the increase of effective power was within approximately 1.7 and 1.9; and approximately between 1.95 and 2.4 times compared to a single Barge, for 2 Urban Barges sailing in convoy and side by side, respectively. For 3 Urban barges sailing

in convoy, the increment in effective power ranges within 2.6 and 2.9 times compared to the Urban barge sailing individually.

In Figure 35 one may observe that the wave amplitude leaving the bottom of the barge near the stern increases, at $T = 0.6$ m.

Figure 30 - Second invariant $Q=10$ coloured by nondimensional helicity for the 2UB C sailing at 13 km/h at $T = 0.4$ m.

As the speed of the barge increases, the wave amplitude leaving the bottom of the barge near the stern increases, especially at $T = 0.6$ m, as it can be observed in Figure 36 (left). The wave pattern for the Urban barge sailing at different speeds in shallow water is represented in Figure 36 (right) for $h/T = 2.0$.

Figure 31 - (left) Free-surface topology at different speeds and various drafts for 2UB SBS; (right) Free-surface topology at a speed of 13 km/h and canal depth to draft ratio $h/T = 2.0$

Resistance prediction for the Urban barge showed that the wave making components are significant, which may be related to the geometry of the hull, especially the underwater part. This requires special considerations to optimize the hull form to reduce this effect.

The analysis of the barge in shallow water was presented showing that the simulation complies with the theory for all simulation cases. Resistance increases severely as the canal depth decreases, and

as the ship’s speed increases. Increment in resistance at some cases were up to 4.5 times compared to that in deep water.

(iii) The third step is focused on barge global and local strength analysis by 3D finite element models, fully extended over the barge length, side to side. The equilibrium position of the barge in the design equivalent quasi-static waves environment (sagging and hogging), besides the still water case, is obtained by in-house codes, based on a non-linear iterative procedure. As main loading cases of the barge are considered: light ship and full loading with euro pallets, according to the shipbuilding classification societies rules. As assessment criteria, the 3D model admissible stress limit for aluminium material, buckling factor and maximum vertical deflection are considered. Also, the freeboard criterion is considered. The results of the study estimate the safety and integrity structural limits, providing technical information for improving the barge’s structure improvement, and to ensure the strength safety rules requirements.

The next table 6 presents the operation cases of the barge, according to classification society rules, in which LCG is longitudinal center of gravity, Δ is ship displacement, and $T_{msw, A, F}$ represents the medium drought for still water aft and fore respectively.

Table 6 - Barge loading cases

Table : Barge loading cases			
LCG = 30 m	Light structure	Light ship with equipment	Full load (euro pallets)
Δ [t]	4.25	8.1	27.5
$T_{msw, A, F}$ [m]	0.353 0.216	0.48 0.307	0.796 0.803

Table 7 presents the strength criteria used for the barge structure analysis assessment.

Table 7 - The strength and freeboard criteria

Table : The strength and freeboard criteria	
$\sigma_{vonMadm}$ [MPa]	100
$B_{buckling_adm}$	1.30
w_{adm} [mm]	30
Free board $min[m]$	0.3

Figure 32 - Equilibrium position in still water and EDW, for light ship with equipment

Figure 32 gives the equilibrium position in still water and EDW for light ship case with equipment.

Figures 33 present the vertical displacement and equivalent von Mises stress distribution for sagging EDW, $h_w=0.6$ m, full loading case with euro pallets.

Figure 33 – Vertical displacement (w)[mm]-sagging EDW, hw=0.6m - full-with euro pallets (case 3)

Figure 34 - Equivalent von Misses stress(vonM) [MPa] – sagging EDW, hw=0.6m - full with euro pallets (case3)

For the studied loading cases analysed in this study, light ship with equipment and full loading case with euro pallets, the admissible stress and vertical deflection criteria are fulfilled for still water and maximum EDW height in sagging and hogging conditions.

According to the buckling structural instability situation occurred (during buckling analysis), it is recommended to add anti - buckling constructive detail elements for the starboard and portside bottom longitudinal girders. After implementing the recommended constructive updates, it is recommended to reassess the buckling behaviour for the hull structure.

3.4.3. Use case 3: Environmental alert system

Impact of the use of the urban vessel on the environment.

We calculated already that **the zero emission electric urban vessel ensures a CO₂ reduction of 97.528 kilograms per year compared to 2 diesel trucks of 10 Ton. This is the equivalent of CO₂ absorption of 8.13 hectare forest surface.** To better understand these figures : 8,13 hectares forest is the equivalent of 12 soccer fields.

We will further investigate the social and environmental impact of the use of this type of vessel in the project.

Network of measurement points of the water level in Flanders

In Flanders, a very extensive network has already been installed to measure and monitor the water level from a distance. These measuring points are fixed measuring points on the land side near flood-prone areas, lock complexes and rivers.

Figure 35 - Water level measuring point in Flanders

Source : Ministry of Public Works : <https://www.waterinfo.be/Themas#item=overstroming/actueel>

These measuring points provide detailed information about the water level and can even make a short-term prediction (up to 10 days) based on historical data. This can be used to build application scenarios.

Figure 36 - Detail of a water level measuring point

Also, the Flemish water authority, who controls and manages 1.050 km of IW, had a database with the real life data of 335 measuring points on the shoreside (see: <https://www.visuris.be/hydrometeo>).

This transmits the current water level and the flow data of the river or canal where the sensor is located.

ACTUELE WATERSTAND EN DEBIET GEGEVENS

Filters	Locatie	Parameter	Waarde	Meettijdstip	Tijdsreeks	Data Status
Parameter	Aarschot	Debiet	7,70 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:20	Pv	Actief
<input type="checkbox"/> Debiet	Afwaarts/Demer	Debiet	0,01 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:15	Pv	Actief
<input type="checkbox"/> Waterstand	Damme/Leopoldkl	Debiet	0,01 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:15	Pv	Actief
Locatie	Deinze/Leie	Debiet	-5,65 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 10:30	Pv	Actief
<input type="text"/>	Eppegem/Zenne	Debiet	6,17 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:20	Pv	Actief
Tijdsreeks	Erembodegem/De...	Debiet	8,62 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 10:30	Pv	Geen recente data
<input type="checkbox"/> 60Gem	Evergem/Ringvaart	Debiet	4,91 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:20	Pv	Actief
<input type="checkbox"/> Pv	Gavere/Bovensche...	Debiet	14,40 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:15	Pv	Actief
Data status	Ham Sluis	Debiet	3,56 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:20	Pv	Actief
<input type="checkbox"/> Actief	Vijzelkanaal/Alber...	Debiet	3,56 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:20	Pv	Actief
<input type="checkbox"/> Geen Recente Data	Haringe/Ijzer	Debiet	0,47 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 12:15	Pv	Actief
Wis Filters	Hasselt Sluis	Debiet	6,38 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 10:40	Pv	Actief
	Vijzelkanaal/Alber...	Debiet	6,38 m ³ /s	28/05/2023 10:40	Pv	Actief

Figure 37 - Actual water levels of waterways in Flanders

In order to get a complete picture of the water balance, in addition to precipitation and precipitation intensity, various other meteorological parameters are measured at several locations in Flanders. This measurement data is used to calculate the potential evapotranspiration (pET), which is the maximum amount of soil moisture that plants can evaporate or that can evaporate directly from the soil.

Potential evapotranspiration is calculated using the Penman-Montheith formula. For this calculation, the temperature at different heights above the ground, the air pressure, the relative humidity, the wind direction and speed, the irradiation flux through the sun, and the ground heat flux are measured. From this data, in addition to the potential evapotranspiration, the dew point temperature is also calculated. The soil temperature is also measured at several locations.

Because there are no sensors in the city center of Ghent, despite the fact that there is also a time-sensitive area there, and no sensory information is available for use in test cases in other European countries, it is a good idea to equip the ship with sensors that can measure and transmit information about the water level to the CC.

Figure 38 - Actual water measure point fixed on quay in North Sea Port in Flanders

In this use case, some sensors will be installed on the vessels, for environmental data gathering, which will be stored on the cloud and used by the partners. These sensors will provide information about water level, stream, air pollution, CO₂, NO_x emissions. Therefore, in case of alert, the signal from the sensors will be able to raise in time the alarm to government and crisis institutions. Some sensors are already installed on the ship, but particular attention should be paid to those additional sensors

that are needed. The data fed back by the sensors are also necessary for the development of prediction models, as demonstrated clearly in the use case 1.

The most important involved parties are the public environmental services, such as the Flanders Environment Agency (VMM), research institutions and rescue teams as well.

Input ICCS : For the extension of water level sensors network, new state-of-the-art in-situ sensors will be installed so as to enable accurate monitoring at designated locations with high temporal resolution. These in-situ water level data will be combined with free data coming from Copernicus Sentinel-3 altimetry satellite data towards the extraction of information about the dynamics of the inland water levels. Also, forecasting models will be built enabling the prediction of the time evolution of water level changes in the areas of interest.

Furthermore, water quality sensors will be installed to monitor water quality related information of the marine environment. Some of parameters, such as suspended sediments, turbidity, chlorophyll, temperature of water, pH, free chlorine, and heavy metals could be affected by vessel navigation and play major role in the environment, and therefore to the environmental alert system.

3.4.4. Use case 4: Floating Energy System

The study of use case 4 can be decomposed to the two following parts: i) use of batteries for the propulsion of the urban vessel and ii) use of the batteries installed on the vessels, so as the platform can operate as a giant power supply infrastructure.

Regarding the first remark, the barges will be sailing using the power of the electric system combined with an extended battery system. This configuration will eventually evolve into a floating power supply to be used not only in crisis, but also in normal circumstances. The batteries to be installed on the existing vessels and the one developed, will provide an alternative source of power for propulsion, for a long range. They may be installed either “inside” the barge or on the deck, on top of the barge. It is important to highlight that a combination of both systems can be exploited. For example, when a ship is not sailing, it does not consume power and the available battery can be used for other purposes. Once again, the autonomous sailing vessels will be deployed with remote control from the MCC.

As earlier in this section mentioned, not only for propulsion, but also as a huge power supply for cascading effects, the battery will be exploited as floating off-grid power supplier (to a hospital or crisis center for example). The use of large battery systems for emergency situations is definitely an overarching goal. The charging capacity of the batteries and generally the energy management system for monitoring the consumption of the fuel, will provide information, available on the cloud, which will be used for the development of several prediction models.

The most actively involved parties are the public grid network operators, private constructors with need for energy-as-a-service, emergency units and grid back-up systems.

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN : Key milestones and timeplan

ICCS : ICCS is planning to install water level sensors during winter, between December of 2023 and January of 2024, while water quality sensors will be installed at the beginning of the coming year. ICCS is working to a scoping review paper for the inland water level monitoring by satellites observations, which will be published until November of 2023.

OHB : Detailing the step-by-step implementation plan

- Close the analysis for the Smart Terminal
- Define with UGal and shipyard the final construction plan for the hull of the vessel – M16
- Finalise the environmental study and define sensors by Sintef,... - M16
- Purchase sensors for the environmental system by Sintef,... M17
- Define with SF and UGal the propulsion system for the vessel – M16
- Define the transport box design – M17
- Purchase of material for vessel and Transport box (alu, engine, spare parts, ...) – M18
- Finalise the study of the battery pack and EMS for the “floating Energy” use case - M18
- Purchase battery packs and software. Start engineering energy system – M20
- Select mobile crane or loading system for the ship – M20
- Purchase mobile loading system – M21
- Finalising the construction of the smart vessel and start testing remote control with SF - M30
- Set up testbed for the several sub use cases (sensor testing, remote control of ship and crane, switch remote control via DT to another shore control center, test transporbox, etc...)

4 Application Scenario's

The ReNEW project is a research and innovation initiative that seeks to promote resilience and sustainability in inland waterway transport. For Living Lab 1 in Belgium we want to set up some application scenario's.

Together with the LL1 partners and ITA and INL and VLTN application scenario's will be designed as described in the proposal.

1. Impact of the loss of staff in the Smart Terminal or in logistic operations. When the staff working in a terminal is disabled due to an external calamity or a pandemic, the system or procedure developed by ITA must switch the work to a level of automation so that the Smart terminal as a whole can continue to function. The personnel of a terminal (logistics manager, operator of the crane or loading installation, terminal operator, warehouseman, skipper, sailor, ...) can fail in this scenario, jeopardizing the functioning of the terminal operations. This Renew project wants to find an answer to this by automating the operation of a terminal to a high degree. In addition, the scenario can be tested when there is a 10% loss of personnel, 20%, The time element within which a switchover from human-driven actions is taken over by machine-driven actions is an important factor in this.
2. Map the resilience of the existing infrastructure and policy makers in a country in setting up emergency plans in answer to disasters is an overarching task in all LL. The impact of the consequences of climate change has increased significantly in recent years. There are examples of this every month in Europe with far-reaching consequences for the population, infrastructure, ... and society. Examples such as the great flood in Belgium in Pepinster on July 19, 2021, May 19 in Italy in the Emilia-Romagna region and on May 24, 2023 in Spain (Regions of Valencia, Murcia and Andalucia) have a terrible impact on society with a lot of dead, homeless and human suffering. Setting up an analysis model of the different responses to climate disasters may limit the impact of these phenomena. The following matters can be investigated: Life of Planning, Preparedness of the region and policymakers, Response of the policymakers, crises centers and rescue institutions and the existing of a Recovery and help program.
3. Render of the operations in the Smart Terminal. Imec has already worked out some ideas regarding the visualization of the operation of the Smart terminal whereby various elements are visualized (ship position, data from the environment, size of the ramp, position of the crane during loading and unloading,...) . This animation enables us to visualize the operation of the Smart Terminal for all parties involved. It can also be used for instructional purposes for policy makers and rescue personnel.

4.1 ITA - Smart Terminal Simulation

In UC1 Smart Terminal, the impact of staff loss on the Smart Terminal or logistic operations will be addressed by simulation. The objective is to enable the Smart Terminal to continue functioning even in scenarios where personnel are disabled due to external calamities or pandemics. The approach undertaken will involve obtaining comprehensive information, data, and parameters pertaining to the terminal. A thorough assessment of the terminal's current state, including operational procedures, staff roles, and workflow dependencies, will be conducted to construct a baseline scenario as a reference point for analysis.

Subsequently, business processes within the terminal will be meticulously mapped using advanced techniques of business process modelling. This will enable the identification of key processes that are most susceptible to automation. Each process will be carefully analysed to determine critical junctures where the transition from human-driven actions to machine-driven actions can be seamlessly integrated.

In addition, various variables influencing the terminal's processes will be identified. Factors such as workload fluctuations, external conditions, and resource availability will be considered to design a resilient and adaptive automated system.

Cutting-edge technologies that have the potential to enhance the terminal's overall performance will be explored. Technologies like Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Robotic Process Automation will be evaluated for their suitability in complementing human labor and maintaining efficient operations during staff loss scenarios.

Based on the gathered information, process mapping, and technology assessment, a comprehensive simulation model will be constructed. This model will be sensitive to the various factors and capable of simulating different scenarios of staff loss, such as 10%, 20%, or more. The model will gauge the time element required for the seamless switchover from human-driven to machine-driven actions, a critical factor in ensuring uninterrupted terminal operations during personnel incapacitation.

Figure 39 - Example of a Business Process Diagram

Through analysis of the model under different scenarios, informed recommendations will be made, and optimal strategies proposed to the ReNEW project team. These recommendations will help in the formulation of a robust and efficient system that can dynamically adapt to unforeseen staff loss situations, ensuring the continuous functioning of the Smart Terminal and its logistic operations. By employing this proactive approach, the ReNEW project aims to fortify the terminal against potential disruptions and contribute to the advancement of automation in the maritime industry.

The timeline below reflects a high-level overview of the evaluation plan. The duration of each phase may vary based on the complexity of the processes, the availability of data, and the extent of simulation refinement required. Regular communication and collaboration with stakeholders, especially during workshops, will be crucial to ensure the success of the automation evaluation project.

Phase 1: Preliminary Assessment

- Conduct initial meetings with stakeholders to define use case scope and objectives.
- Gather comprehensive information, data, and parameters related to the terminal's current operations and staff roles.
- Identify key personnel and subject matter experts for process mapping.

Phase 2: Process Mapping and Analysis

- Organize workshops with relevant stakeholders to map the terminal's existing processes and workflows.
- Utilize business process modelling techniques to document the mapped processes and identify potential automation points.

- Analyze the processes to determine critical areas for automation and understand the impact of staff loss.

Phase 3: Technology Assessment

- Conduct research and assess cutting-edge automation technologies, including Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Robotic Process Automation.
- Evaluate the suitability of each technology for specific processes and scenarios.
- Identify simulation software or platforms suitable for creating a virtual environment for evaluating automation scenarios.

Phase 4: Model Development

- Develop a comprehensive simulation model that incorporates the processes identified for automation.
- Integrate the selected automation technologies into the simulation to replicate the switchover from human-driven to machine-driven actions.
- Validate the model using historical data and performance metrics to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Phase 5: What-if Scenarios

- Introduce various scenarios of staff loss, such as 10%, 20%, and more, into the simulation model.
- Analyze the model's response to different scenarios to identify vulnerabilities and optimize the automation process.
- Conduct iterative tests to fine-tune the model based on the scenarios results.

Phase 6: Workshops and Scenario Evaluation

- Organize workshops with stakeholders to present the simulation scenarios and gather feedback.
- Evaluate the performance and effectiveness of the automated processes under different staff loss scenarios.
- Collaborate with stakeholders to identify areas of improvement and refine the simulation model.

Phase 7: Final Report and Recommendations

- Compile the findings, analysis, and workshop feedback into a comprehensive final report.
- Provide actionable recommendations based on the simulation results for optimizing terminal operations during staff loss situations.

- Present the final report to stakeholders, highlighting key insights and proposed strategies.

4.2 ITA - IWT and urban logistics

This task involves addressing the key challenge faced by LL1, which is to set up a multipurpose scenario capable of support Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) during crises. During standard operations, the synchronization of freight arrival via barges with various compatible transport modes, aligning with the City of Ghent's commitment to environmental sustainability and an enhanced quality of living, will be efficiently managed by City Logistics Hubs. Among these modes are cargo bikes and electric vehicles, enabling the seamless movement of both freight and people within and beyond the city. However, in situations where cargo arrives at the City Logistics Hub via inland waterways, the existence of suitable infrastructure becomes essential to ensure swift and efficient cargo offloading from the barges onto urban logistic transport modes.

To address this challenge, the first step will involve the gathering of comprehensive information from the City Logistics Hubs. Data related to their current operations, infrastructure, and capacities will be collected to form a solid foundation for the simulation model. Additionally, historical data on previous orders, including delivery times, volume, and destinations, will be collected to inform the simulation's input parameters.

Subsequently, a simulation model will be developed that incorporates multi-agent technology and encompasses the dynamics of various entities, such as barges, cargo vehicles, city logistics hubs, and urban transport modes. By integrating the historical data and information gathered from the City Logistics Hubs, the simulation will accurately replicate real-world scenarios and provide a reliable basis for assessing different crisis situations.

Figure 40 - Prototype virtual model IWT and urban logistics

With advanced technologies at its core, the simulation model will enable the evaluation of alternative scenarios. By performing what-if analyses, the simulation will shed light on critical factors such as cargo handling efficiency, barge unloading rates, synchronization of urban transport modes, or response times during crisis events.

To further enhance the analysis, the simulation model will dynamically calculate operational, economic, and environmental Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs may include the number of orders delivered on time, lead time, transportation and handling costs, fuel consumption, and CO2 emissions. By quantifying these metric, decision-makers will gain valuable insights into the overall performance and sustainability of the City Logistics Hubs and IWT operations.

The proposed methodology aims to provide decision-makers with a robust and data-driven tool for strategically optimizing the synchronization of transportation modes and fostering effective crisis management within the City Logistics Hubs. The simulation-based analysis, incorporating dynamically calculated KPIs, will facilitate evidence-based decision-making and contribute to the sustainable advancement of inland waterway transport and urban logistics, aligning with the City of Ghent's overarching goals. Through this endeavour, the aim is to fortify the logistics infrastructure, promoting a harmonious and resilient ecosystem that aligns with the city's commitment to environmental sustainability and an enhanced quality of life.

Real life demonstrations will be held with partners as Ugal, Seafar, OHB, ...

1. Demonstration with several rescue urban boats from OHB which will set up a rescue scenario to the pontoon in cooperation with Ugal 's FMP. In this demonstration the impact of floods in a dense area of a city environment will test the rescue of people and material in a rapid deployment.
2. Resilience of the Command Center. The impact of a disaster (as for ex. Floods, fire,...) on the logistic infrastructure can be tested by moving the web based interface with the data stream connection with the Smart Terminal from the onshore Command Center to another Command center.
3. Develop autonomous platooning capability : Demonstration of the impact of a road obstruction by using the urban vessels in a vessel train of platooning mode, on the one hand with a physical connection and on the other hand with a digital connection by Seafar with 2 remote controlled vessels. This FMP model can rescue a lot of people and transport a high number of goods.
4. Demonstration of solutions where water obstruction can block the waterway.
5. The testing of the effectiveness of the GALILEO positioning system in managing the vessels from the onshore Command Center. Switch from GPS and GALILEO will prove the resilience in the communication channels and systems between ships and CC.
6. Test the readiness of the floating power system to provide power in emergency situations when the grid fails and essential installations require power. This floating power system is an elaboration of a flexibly resilient grid power installation that can be used anywhere within the range of the vessels.

5 Conclusions

5.1 Conclusions for the 4 Living Labs

The ReNEW project is a research and innovation initiative that seeks to promote resilience and sustainability in inland waterways transport (IWT). The project is driven by a demonstrative core composed of four real-life Living Labs, which are focused on complementary aspects of Green Resilient IWT. These Living Labs are designed to ensure the required interrelations towards achieving innovation synergies and creating a comprehensive contextual approach towards a resilient and thriving IWT future.

The four Living Labs act as distinct areas or regions and are supported by local authorities, involved stakeholders from the inland waterways sector, shippers, boat owners, operators, as well as stakeholders from the inland transport supply chain. The Living Labs follow the common ReNEW implementation process, but each has a distinct ambition and scope on how to approach the goal of resilience and sustainability.

To achieve the goal of resilience and sustainability, a different mix of technologies under a single framework, have been developed in a single optimum adoption scenario for each Living Lab. Specific key performance indicators (KPIs) reflecting the impacts that each Living Lab envisions to achieve are currently being defined. This report provides a preliminary list of these KPIs and lists the technologies/measures of the optimum scenario that will be adopted for their achievement.

Dedicated timeplans along with the optimum implementation plans are also under development and will be presented during the next reports. The implementation plans will continue to be updated as the planning and design work becomes more detailed.

As part of the project, the as-is conditions for both physical and digital infrastructure, together with information about existing models, data sets, and tools and key stakeholders, were collected through this report and formed input to the planning and design work of all of ReNEW's activities so far. This information is critical in developing a comprehensive approach to promoting resilience and sustainability in IWT.

The work performed in conjunction with this report includes the framework for resilience and sustainability and all relevant aspects as they relate to Green Resilient IWT, the social dimension and the stakeholder engagements, definition and development of the objectives regarding the DT and Dataspaces technology and use cases, and the Living Labs evaluation framework, including the list of KPIs and assessment methodologies for the impact assessment. Dedicated reports with the outcomes of the work on each of these subjects will be produced in the following months from corresponding Work Packages.

5.2 Conclusions for the LL1 Belgium

Living Lab 1 Belgium in the ReNEW project is a research and innovation laboratory with real life application scenario's that will prove resilience and sustainability in inland waterways transport (IWT).

As the basis of the project, information was collected from the various levels of the project design for both the physical and the digital infrastructure, the knowledge of the inland waterways for developing a tailor-made design of a new type of resilient and zero-emission ship, together with information about data sets and tools.

The partners participating in the LL 1 work as a task force to combine the best elements to develop a comprehensive approach to promote resilience and sustainability in the LL, and by extension, inland navigation as a whole.

As described in the above report, the society faces many challenges caused by climate change. These changes often have a negative impact on people, the environment and the planet. With the research into sustainable and resilient solutions for setting up a "smart terminal" and smart logistics systems, we want to provide an answer to these unpredictable disasters in order to limit the damage as much as possible.

We want to demonstrate that this smart terminal and associated solutions can be remotely controlled to a large extent outside the affected impact zone.

By combining the knowledge and strengths of the specialized partners, we try to arrive at a state-of-the-art solution that can be used in many ways. There is a lot of premium knowledge and experience in this consortium, which means that we can set high expectations in the elaboration of the various digital, physical and operational objectives.

As a final outcome, we will work in the coming years towards an operationally working ecosystem that we can test in a real life setting, being the city center of Ghent and the surrounding areas and waterways.

Peter Geirnaert - OHB

6 Appendix

6.1 Appendix 1 - References in literature and online

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6.2 Appendix 2 - Projects : lessons learned from other European projects

ST4W: Smart Track for Waterway proposes a management solution for shipment by inland waterway transport, providing to small stakeholders a simpler and cheaper access to secure data, and enabling them to share a hierarchical track & trace service of shipment at logistics unit level. (Interreg NWE IVB)

<http://www.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/st4w-smart-tracking-data-network-for-shipment-by-inlandwaterway/>

AVATAR: In several modern cities in the EU the existing waterways will be used as much as possible for urban distribution. This not only includes parcel services and delivery of shop supplies. Building projects within the LEZ, garbage collection, event supplies, ferry and shuttle services, etc. are also eligible. AVATAR unmanned electric boats will not bring about CO₂ emissions or noise pollution but contribute to traffic reduction in the city centres. Clearly, electrically-powered vessels will not run on electricity from nuclear power stations, which will eventually disappear, nor on electricity from fossil fuels, because advanced European cities want to achieve energy independence. The vessels will run on energy from RES, generated by large PV installations on the roofs of sheds and SME buildings located on the waterways outside the city centre. As the sun does not shine at night, as much solar energy as possible, but also wind energy, will be stored in hydrogen at daytime. In AVATAR, the starting point is as follows :

- Renewable energy generated in the Port of Ghent is stored in hydrogen.
- At night, an ICE CHP running on H₂ converts the hydrogen into electricity that allows the electric city distribution vessels to charge their batteries. While the ICE CHP is charging the vessels, heat is released.
- In the AVATAR approach this heat will be stored in a buffer tank that is part of the central heating installation of, for example, an SME. In practice, the heat could also be transferred to the Ghent district heating network. It goes without saying that the CHP heat will be put to good use.

Connecting Citizen Ports 21 century (Interreg NWE IVB)

DIPCITY (Interreg NEW IIIB, 2001-2007)

RIS Implementation in Belgium (CEF): RIS Implementation in Belgium (CEF) : [file:///C:/Users/Dell/AppData/Local/Packages/Microsoft.MicrosoftEdge_8wekyb3d8bbwe/TempState/Downloads/2014-be-tm-0238-m2014-be-tm-0238-m%20\(1\)](file:///C:/Users/Dell/AppData/Local/Packages/Microsoft.MicrosoftEdge_8wekyb3d8bbwe/TempState/Downloads/2014-be-tm-0238-m2014-be-tm-0238-m%20(1))

Tide2Use: Development of an AI-assisted algorithm to support traffic management for one of their sealocks in the Port of Bremen under a funding scheme of the German Ministry for Transportation and Digital Infrastructure. Objective of the project is to reduce the electrical energy consumption of the pumping system of a sealock by optimising the traffic flow to allow for tide-driven replenishment of the harbour basins behind the lock. Core of the project is to intelligently manage the competition for the incoming tide. At the same time, vessels use the flood to access the Port of Bremen and it is used to replenish the water lost by operating the lock.

Artificial intelligence will provide decision support for operations staff at the lock when to use the incoming tide for water replenishment without compromising the service level for shipping. The project will generate “guaranteed” lock opening times which can be used to feed other traffic management systems.

binntelligent In national and international freight transport, German inland ports represent an important link between inland waterways and other modes of transport. The project develops intelligent algorithms to increase the forecasting accuracy of processes along IW-intermodal supply chains. A platform provides real-time accessible information for all parties along a supply chain to monitor, forecast and control vessel movements. This is in particular important for inland ports to make handling resources available on a just-in-time basis, as well as for efficient lock operation along inland waterways to avoid congestion and reduce waiting times. Through IT-supported communication between inland navigation, seaports, inland ports and connecting transport modes, binntelligent will also create the prerequisites for future synchromodal transport concepts. <https://www.isl.org/en/news/intelligent-information-technologies-the-inlandport-the-future-kick-start-binntelligent>

EGNSS Hull-to-Hull: The overall objective of the proposal is to address the need of the maritime community to safely navigate in close proximity of other vessels and objects, being stationary or moving. This will assist mariners in making correct navigation decisions. And further, this will be a fundamental requirement for autonomous vessels. (EU-H2020, 2017-2020). <https://www.mech.kuleuven.be/en/pma/research/robotics/research/applications/imp/ais/gnss-hull-2-hull-project>

Autonom varen in de Westhoek: As part of the 'Autonomous sailing in the Westhoek' project, the project partners Waterwegen en Zeekanaal NV, the POM West-Vlaanderen and KU Leuven are starting preparations for testing an autonomous sailing vessel on the IJzer. The project aims to test the technology for unmanned sailing in a real-life environment, on the IJzer between Heernisse (Diksmuide) and the Sint-Joris reservoir (Nieuwpoort). (EFRO,2017-2019). <https://www.mech.kuleuven.be/en/pma/research/robotics/research/applications/imp/ais/autonom-varen-in-dewesthoek>

Towards Autonomous Inland Shipping: Septentrio bestows Ecochallenge Award for the proposal to use highprecision high-reliability Galileo receivers to modernize inland waterway transport by introducing autonomoustechnology for the vessels. (FWO-SB, 2017-2021).

<https://www.mech.kuleuven.be/en/pma/research/robotics/research/applications/imp/ais/fwo-sb-tais>

LEARN - Logistics Emission Accounting and Reduction Network: LEARN empowers business to reduce their carbon footprint across their global logistics supply chains. Logistics emissions measurement, reporting and verification (MRV) is improved and accelerated by LEARN. SFC coordinated LEARN building on its role as a multi-modal, global facilitator raising the profile of the logistics sector and its potential to contribute to step changes in improved energy efficiency and emissions reduction. SFC also leveraged its significant existing network developed through the smart freight leadership network, and its work on Global Green Freight Action Plan and in coordinating GLEC. SFC also led the dissemination and exploitation work package, again leveraging its existing network and the expertise of its staff in delivering successful targeted dissemination campaigns.

AEOLIX - Architecture for EurOpean Logistics Information eXchange: SFC worked on the impact assessment of the AEOLIX platform. SFC's role was mostly to apply the GLEC Framework to calculate GHG emissions related KPIs. CO2 calculation is a side service offered by the AEOLIX platform.

THT - Transforming Heavy Transport: THT aims to develop a WMB strategy and business community of practice to tackle emissions from transport, focusing on heavy transport such as freight, shipping and aviation. SFC is appointed by WBCSD to complete one of the key outcomes related to broaden the stakeholder agreement on how business commitments on heavy transport can be translated in to business processes and operations. In detail, SFC is in charge for completing: Overview of relevant business processes, overview of logistics procurement best practices, agreed framework for sustainable logistics procurement guidance.

PiLoNav: In the project PiLoNav (Precise and integer Localisation and Navigation in Rail and Inlandwater Traffic (2010-2014)), funded by the Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology (BMWV), a sensor fusion system (location platform) was developed, which can be used for accurate location, navigation and time data determination. This platform was the bases for the development of innovative applications within the area of railway and inland water traffic using operative traffic management systems and advanced driver assistance systems.

LAESSI: Within the project LAESSI (Control and Assistance Systems to Enhance the Safety of Navigation in

Inland Waterways efficient navigation assistance functionalities for the inland waterway transport based on high accurate and reliable PNT data have been developed. Here an RTK approach was used in order to support driver assistant functions like a bridge height warning system and an auto pilot for inland waterways.

SCIPPER: Within the currently running project SCIPPER (2018-2021) a driver assistant for automatically entering waterway locks will be developed. For the provision of PNT data a combination of real time Precise Point Positioning (PPP) and close-range sensors like laser scanners will be applied.

ENEL Smart Plant: Development and on the field evaluation of a large scale IoT compliant monitoring system based on embedded wireless sensor devices able to detect faults in mechanical equipments. The output of this project is PlantOne. (July 2015)

Smart PlantOne: funded by BEinCPPS OC1 (Grant agreement n° 680633), such experiment aims at the realization of the preliminary technological improvement of PlantOne toward the Smart Gateway. (2017)

Smart PlantOne: funded by the Horizon2020 (SME-Instruments – Ph.1, Grant agreement n° 790208), the project realise the feasibility study about a system capable to democratise the predictive maintenance implementation on small-medium sized machineries, thought for both SMEs and large firms. (2018).

Smart PlantOne has implemented a prototype tailored for galvanisation plants where the danger is high, and the workers safety is a must. They propose a distributed sensor network based on the several IoT protocols, thus implementing a pervasive monitoring system capable of:

- o Warning locally and remotely operators about machineries malfunctioning and environmental anomalies (e.g., presence of harmful gases);
- o Improving the worker safety;
- o Enforcing high risk environments remote control.

The interoperability characteristic of NGS products permits integrating their systems with Cloud based frameworks for risk and process management along with real time data collection from the field improves functionalities like:

- o Risk & Opportunity Management frameworks;
- o LEAN manufacturing frameworks
- o Manufacturing Execution System

ICONET: funded by the Horizon2020 (Grant agreement n° 769119), the project aims at the realisation of the very first example of Physical Internet network, where the IoT enablement allows a continuous and capillary monitoring on the goods along the logistics chain. (01/09/2018 - 28/02/2021) - www.iconetproject.eu

TAXIBARGE: financed collaboration with i-TRANS, VNF and Northern France Region for a research period of 4 years on Reactive Decision Support Systems for Barge Freight Transportation <http://www.nordpasdecals.vnf.fr/projet-taxibarge-a2242.html>

IRT Railenium: rail transportation; infrastructure enhancement studies

SELIS: VLTN is developing planning and optimization tools for collaborative logistics hubs. (2015-2019)

CORE: VLTN developed solutions for security and resilience in supply chains based on Cloud and Big Data Technologies. It developed supply chain knowledge graphs from data captured from the operational systems of thousands of supply chains and trade lanes, on which Big Data analytics can help decision makers understand better the compliance security and other risks associated with each supply chain. (01/05/2014 - 30/04/2018) - <http://www.coreproject.eu>

EUTravel: VLTN built travel recommendation intelligent assistants on the Cloud, by utilising Open and Linked Data, and Machine Learning Techniques. (Horizon 2020) (2014-2017)

ADAM4eve: The main idea of ADAM4eve is to explore the potential of adaptive materials and structure in ship and pave the way for industrial application. This will allow ships to react more flexible to changing operational and environmental conditions. (FP7, 2013-2015)
<http://www.adam4eve-project.eu>

SMARTyards: The main objective of SMARTYards is to improve the productivity and efficiency of production progress of small and medium European yards, by at least 20% during the three years. (FP7, 2013-2016) <http://www.smartyards-project.eu>

FIBRESHIP: The goal is to enable the construction of the entire hull and superstructure of large-length, seagoing and inland ships in fibre-reinforced plastic (FRP) materials by overcoming several key technical challenges. (H2020, 2017-2020) <http://www.fibreship.eu/>

PROMINENT: Address the key needs for technological development, as well as the barriers to innovation and greening in the European inland navigation sector. (H2020, 2015-2018)
<http://www.prominent-iwt.eu/>

CEE Riverbridge: Development of a new racking system where different loading units like containers, trailers, or even complete trucks can be stored on inland waterway vessels. (Martec, 2015- 2017) CEE Riverbridge was investigating a novel concept capable of stimulating a modal shift from road towards inland navigation with respect to the transportation of goods. This novel concept incorporates the integration of a racking system into a barge onto which different loading units (e.g. containers, trailers or complete trucks) can be stacked. Based on this innovative system, the feasibility of a regular service along the upper Danube section needed to be verified.
<https://www2.ffg.at/verkehr/projekte.php?id=1462&lang=en>

INWAPO: project aim to activate this unexploited potential of waterborne transport in central Europe and also the role of the river and sea ports to achieve better inter-modality of inland and sea ports.
<https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/upgrading-inland-waterway-and-sea-ports>

imFluss: Optimized Traffic Management for Inland Waterway Transport. (IV2Splus 09/2012 – 08/2014)

EMILIA: Electric Mobility for Innovative Freight Logistics in Austria. (Austrian Electric Mobility Flagship Projects – 5th call for proposals 06/2014 – 11/2017)

SmartCT: Smart Container Trucking (National project: Austrian Mobility of the Future, 10th call for proposals 09/2018 – 08/2020)

Inned: Innovative network design (National project: Austrian Mobility of the Future, 7th call for proposals 03/2017 – 02/2018)

PROMINENT - Promoting Innovation in the Inland Waterways Transport Sector (H2020)
<http://www.prominent-iwt.eu/>

DAPhNE – Danube Ports Network (Interreg DTP)

DANTE - Improving Administrative Procedures and Processes for Danube IWT
<http://www.interregdanube.eu/approved-projects/dante> (Interreg DTP, 01/2017 – 06/2019)

LNG Masterplan for Rhine-Main-Danube (TEN-T)

CEE Riverbridge - CEE Riverbridge along the Rhine-Danube Corridor (MARTEC)

REWWay – Research and Education in Inland Waterway Transport (national funding)

T&Tnet: Travel & Transport Solutions Through Emotional Social Networking - Ambient assisted living joint programme

FP7-SME-2012 WINDTURBARS: “On-line Intelligent Diagnostics and Predictive Maintenance Sensor System Integrated within the Wind Turbine Bus-Bar structure to aid Dynamic Maintenance Scheduling” (1MEUR total funding, <http://www.windturbars.eu/>): WP Leader “System Requirement and Specification” & Developer of the predictive model.

H2020-FoF-2014 FACTS4WORKERS: “Worker-centric Workplaces in Smart Factories” (NN MEUR total funding, <http://facts4workers.eu/>) WP Leader “Demonstration & Evaluation of Smart Factory Solution”

FP7-SST-2013-RTD-1 LogiCon: “Lean Secure and Reliable Logistic Connectivity for SMEs” (NN MEUR total funding, <http://www.logicon-project.eu/>): Part of the Spanish Living Lab, linking with SMEs.

H2020-ICT-15-2016-2017 - Big Data PPP: Large Scale Pilot actions in sectors best benefitting from data-driven Innovation - TT – Transforming Transport

CCP21 - Connecting Citizen Ports 21 century: brings together 7 major inland ports and intends to promote connectivity and sustainable transport by optimising the organisation of freight logistics and sustainable spatial development of inland ports in North West Europe (NWE). Water transport is the most sustainable, reliable and safe means of transport for freight. (Interreg NWE IVB).
<https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/connecting-citizen-ports-21>

Urbanzen: This project was made in the context of urban mobility improvement for urban freight distribution. It is fully in line with the political context of large initiatives in the field (BESTUFS, CIVITAS, SUGAR, CityLogistics). If several technologic solutions already exist to improve fluidity of traffic, they are only limited to solve the societal and economic issues. Most of the time, they aren't dedicated to the specific problem of last mile delivery which is the most critical in the supply chain delivery process. The concrete target of URBANZEN project was to provide, at European level, an ITS tool to help public authorities to deliver its local mobility plan to the transporter using the most common used tools: its GPS or onboard real-time traffic management system. All the project was constructed around the exploitation of the world promoted TISA-TPEG (Transport Protocol Experts Group - world group promoting language independent multi-modal traffic and travel information) framework.

Urbanwize: this project is dedicated to the development of an ITS fully integrated, multi-actors, open-source oriented reference architecture to help the urban intermodal transport in several business cases. The project will propose to study several cases: real time delivery of construction supplies in centre of a city, exploitation of a realtime TMS (transport management system) by very small SMEs using bicycles for its deliveries. All the solution is developed to be cloud oriented, multi-users. Multitel is in charge in the project of all the technical matters (cloud deployment, sensors for automatic traceability, Human machine interface for central unit management and courier Smartphone). HMI simplicity and traceability process automation are the key innovation factors in the project.

Epick 2.0: Shared IT platform for real-time interconnection services between warehouses and transporters. The project is the result of a practical problem faced by large companies active in the logistics sector. EPick 2.0 will offer stakeholders various value-added services: warehouse scheduling (WMS) based on truck arrival forecast, traceability information exchange (WMS-TMS), shared and targeted geolocation, route optimization and exploitation of LPWAN (low power wide area network) specific IOT for hierachrical tracking of goods using integration of specific sensors at the level of the pallet.

Blockstart - Interreg Vb: Blockchain-based applications for SME competitiveness. The goal of the project is to identify and test all the potential of blockchain tools in 3 of NWE's top 5 sectors (agrofoods, logistics, health). SMEs are unable to develop & implement blockchain solutions alone, with most R&D projects and investments targeting large corporates/the finance sector, and SME-specific solutions are stuck at Technology Readiness Level TRL 4. Blockstart develops and demonstrates 4 blockchain solutions to TRL 6 in 12 SMEs enabling 10% operational efficiency, reducing costs of data errors by 20% and data security by 30%.

CYBELE: it generates innovation and create value in the domain of agri-food, and its verticals in the sub-domains of PA and PLF, CYBELE aspires at demonstrating how the convergence of HPC, Big Data, Cloud Computing and This proposal version was submitted by Frank ARENDT on 12/09/2019 16:28:39 Brussels Local Time. Issued by the Funding & Tenders Portal Submission System. MG-2-6-2019: Moving freight by Water: Sustainable Infrastructure and Innovative Vessels the IoT can revolutionize farming, reduce scarcity and increase food supply, bringing social, economic, and environmental benefits. CYBELE develops large scale HPC-enabled test beds and delivers a distributed big data management architecture and a data management strategy. ICCS provides expertise in the areas of cloud computing and big data. (H2020).

HIDALGO: Simulations with multiple parameters in the areas of healthcare, transition of green technologies, etc. increase the overall complexity and require a cross-sectoral approach for efficient execution of data and computeintensive workloads. HIDALGO addresses this challenge enabling highly accurate simulations, data analytics and data visualization but also by providing knowledge on how to integrate the various workflows and the corresponding data. ICCS provides the scheduling framework and algorithms for managing complex workflows of big-data analytics execution. (H2020-INFRAEDI-2018-1)

Bonseyes: The Bonseyes project aims to develop a platform consisting of a Data Marketplace, Deep Learning Toolbox, and Developer Reference Platforms for organizations wanting to adopt Artificial Intelligence in low power IoT devices (“edge computing”), embedded computing systems, or data center servers (“cloud computing”). (H2020-ICT-01-2016).

ACTiCLOUD: The goal of ACTiCLOUD is to design and implement a new cloud architecture that will enhance resource efficiency by utilizing the resource disaggregation capabilities of the underlying hardware. On top of this, the project will build cloud management support for geographically distributed cloud sites and support for largescale, in-memory databases. (H2020-ICT-06-2016)

CELAR: The goal of the CELAR project is to develop methods and open-source tools for applying and controlling multi-grained, elastic resource provisioning for Cloud applications in an automated manner. This resource allocation is performed through intelligent decision-making. CSLAB through ATHENA is leading the consortium and the technical effort. (FP7-ICT-317790)

ASAP: The project aims to offer an adaptive, highly scalable analytics platform. The project’s vision is to deliver a unified, open-source execution framework for scalable data analytics. The project’s results will be tested in two different use cases: one in the telecommunications data analytics and the other on web content analytics. CSLAB is leading the technical effort. (FP7-ICT-619706).

E2Data: E2Data proposes an end-to-end solution for Big Data deployments that fully exploits and advances the state-of-the-art in infrastructure services by delivering a performance increase of up to 10x for half the cloud resources. It provides a new Big Data software paradigm of achieving the maximum resource utilization for heterogeneous cloud deployments without affecting current Big Data programming norms (i.e., no code changes in the original source). (H2020-ICT-16-2017).

EMMA: “Enhancing freight Mobility and logistics in the BSR by strengthening inland waterway and river sea transport and proMoting new internAtional shipping services”. (Interreg, 01/03/2016 – 28/02/2019) <http://projectemma.eu/>

AutonomSOW: Feasibility study, technology and data management concept for a testing field for automated and autonomous sailing on Spee-Oder-Waterway, (mFund – BMVI Germany, 01/05/2019 – 31/10/2019), <https://www.autonomsoow.de/index.html>

AUTOSHIP: Autonomous Shipping Initiative for European Waters, will build around two EU industrial market and leading technology providers, such as Rolls Royce and Kongsberg, to create a stronger European cluster able to thrust a market worth Billions of Euros in the next decade, bringing new high-skilled jobs and a safer and greener transport in Europe. AUTOSHIP will build and operate 2 R&A vessels and their needed shore control and operation infrastructure, reaching and going over TRL7. (Grant agreement ID: 815012, 2019-2022)
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/221855/factsheet/en>

TRACK & KNOW: Big Data for Mobility Tracking Knowledge Extraction in Urban Areas - (01/01/2018 - 31/12/2020) - <https://trackandknowproject.eu/>

PROFILE: Data Analytics, Data Sources, and Architecture for Upgraded European Customs Risk Management <https://www.profile-project.eu/> - (01/08/2018 - 31/07/2021)

SKEMA: Sustainable Knowledge Platform for the European Maritime and Logistics Industry - (2008-2011) - INLE technical co-ordinator - <http://www.eskema.eu>

e-Freight: European e-Freight capabilities for Co-modal transport - (1/1/10 - 30/06/14) - <http://www.efreightproject.eu>

iCargo: Intelligent Cargo in Efficient and Sustainable Global Logistics Operations - (01/11/2011 - 30/04/2015) - <http://i-cargo.eu/>

eMAR: Upgraded Maritime Transport Information Management - (1/1/12 - 31/12/15) - <http://www.emarproject.eu/>

SAFEPOST: Reuse and Development of Security Knowledge Assets for International Postal Supply Chains - (1/4/12 - 31/3/16) - <http://www.safepostproject.eu>

EUROSKY: Single European Secure Air-cargo Space - (1/4/13-31/3/17)
<http://www.euroskyproject.eu/>

CORE: Consistently Optimised Resilient Secure Global Supply-Chains - (01/05/2014 - 30/04/2018) - <http://www.coreproject.eu/>

Maas4EU: End-to-end Approach for Mobility-as-a-Service tools, business models, enabling framework and

evidence for European seamless mobility - (01/06/2017 – 01/06/2020) - www.maas4eu.eu

MultiCycle: Advanced and sustainable recycling processes and value chains for plastic-based multi-materials

(01/11/2018 - 31/10/2021) - <http://www.multicycle-project.eu>

CTS - Cargo Traffic Simulation: CTS concerned the development of a simulation tool for transport flows in

multi modal transport networks. The CTS tool facilitates investigations into the distribution of transports onto various carriers under variable framing conditions. On the one hand, the supply side (digital transport networks) was implemented in the network model. On the other hand, the source-destination matrices for the transports to be considered were constructed in the demand model. In the simulation/transfer section, potential distribution functions were defined, based on, e.g. generalized costs.

RISING: The EU project RISING has been carried out to exploit and boost the potential of River Information

Services (RIS) for means of voyage planning, fleet management, event management as well as for port and terminal management. <https://www.cross-border.org/core/fp7-project-rising-core3004/>